

Technical Guideline Series

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Values Assessment Directory

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This page is designed to help navigate through all the documents of the values assessment, such as the data management reports, figures and all accompanying documents.

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Full report

- Full report

Summary for policymakers

- SPM
- Translations of the SPM in German and Japanese, and available for downloading in plain text in Arabic, Chinese, French, Russian and Spanish.
- Figures of the SPM
- Tables of the SPM

Factsheet

- Factsheet - Messages from the summary for policymakers

Chapter 1. The role of the values of nature and valuation for addressing the biodiversity crisis and navigating towards more just and sustainable futures

- Chapter 1 and supplementary material
- Figures
- Call for Contributions on Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK)

Chapter 2. Conceptualizing the diverse values of nature and their contributions to people

- Chapter 2 and supplementary material
- Figures
- Tables
- Systematic review of value types in academic literature
- Systematic review on the conceptualizations of values
- Literature review on value articulating institutions
- Literature review on the diverse perspectives on fisheries at the global scale
- Analysis of national and international policy documents related to biodiversity and sustainability
- Behaviour theories literature review
- Literature review regarding values, valuation and decision-making
- Analysis of contributions on the interconnections between languages, biodiversity and values
- Literature review for the philosophies of good living
- Literature review on multiple values concepts in academic literature

Chapter 3. The potential of valuation

- Chapter 3 and supplementary material
- Figures
- Tables
- Systematic PCIV (Principles, Criteria, Indicators, Verifiers) review on valuation methods
- Systematic Review of previous comparative assessments of valuation methods
- Systematic review on Method Families
- Historical development of nature-based valuation methods
- Reviews on IPLC approaches to valuation
- Analysis of Contributions on Values and Valuation Methods by ILK experts and holders
- Valuation Atlas

Chapter 4. Value expression in decision-making

- Chapter 4 and supplementary material
- Figures
- Tables
- Systematic review on motivational crowding by economic incentives in conservation policies
- Literature review on values considered in decision-making contexts at local level
- Systematic review on valuation uptake
- Literature review on outcomes in environmental certification
- Literature & case study review on outcomes in protected areas and indigenous and community conserved areas (ICCAs)
- Literature & case study review on outcomes in payments for ecosystem services / compensation for ecosystem services (PES/CES) programmes
- Literature review on values articulated in agrobiodiversity management
- Review on outcomes in big development projects (mining and dams)
- Literature review for the Amazonia ILK cross-assessment case study (cross-chapter/ILK)
- Coincidence of Aichi target 2 reporting and valuation at country level

Chapter 5. The role of diverse values of nature in visioning and transforming towards just and sustainable futures

- Chapter 5 and supplementary material
- Figures
- Tables
- Role of values in transformative change
- Systematic review of association between values of nature, nature's contributions to people and good quality of life and futures in scenarios, visions and pathways
- Earth Stewardship and Biocultural Conservation projects
- Differences between future archetypes (text similarity analysis)

Chapter 6. Policy options and capacity development to operationalize the inclusion of diverse values of nature in decision-making

- Chapter 6 and supplementary material
- Figures
- Tables
- Text Analysis - Constitutions Pluralistic Value Approach
- Transformative Governance within Policy Instruments and Initiatives
- Brightspot Cases text analysis
- Review of gaps within the chapters of the IPBES Values Assessment

Underlying bibliographic data and research materials

- VA Zotero library